

The Design of English Materials to communication the Identity of Amphawa District, Samut Songkram Province, for Sustainable Tourism

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Abstract—The main purpose of this research was to study how to communicate the identity of the Amphawa district, Samut Songkram province for sustainable tourism. The qualitative data was collected through studying related materials, exploring the area, in-depth interviews with three groups of people: three directly responsible officers who were key informants of the district, twenty foreign tourists and five Thai tourist guides. A content analysis was used to analyze the qualitative data. The two main findings of the study were as follows:

1. The identity of the Amphawa District, Samut Songkram province is the area controlled by Amphawa sub district (sub-municipality). The working unit which runs and looks after Amphawa sub district administration is known as the Amphawa mayor. This establishment was built to be a resort for normal people and tourists visiting the Amphawa district near the Maekong River consisting of rest accommodations. Along the river there is a restaurant where food and drinks are served, rich mangrove forests, a learning center, fireflies and cork trees. The Amphawa district was built to honor and commemorate King Rama II and is where the greatest number of fireflies and cork trees can be seen in Thailand from May to October each year.
2. The communication of the identity of Amphawa District, Samut Songkram Province which the researcher could find and design to present in English materials can be summed up in 5 items: 1) The history of the Amphawa District, Samut Songkram province 2) The history of King Rama II Memorial Park 3) The identity of Amphawa Floating Market 4) The Learning center of Ecosystem: Fireflies and Cork Trees 5) How to keep Amphawa District, Samut Songkram Province for sustainable tourism.

Keywords—Foreigner tourists, signified, semiotics, sustainable tourism.

I. INTRODUCTION

TOURISM is an important industry because it creates income for developing countries. Thailand realizes the importance of continuously developing its tourism industry. The country supports and promotes many activities and projects with advertisements and publications geared toward people who are in this area. Also, Thai people are beginning to realize the importance of preserving their tourism resources and supporting sustainable tourism. Statistics for the first half of 2011 from January to June show an increase in tourism of 14.38 percent or 7,559,528 tourists. The next six months shows an increase of 20.90 percent [9]. This increase in

tourists has boosted many local careers and income as well as helping develop the transportation, basic construction and public utilities in the local communities where tourism is important. The local people are less likely to immigrate to other places with these improvements in their own area.

Tourism in Thailand was recently affected by the changing world economy and natural disasters. The Tourism Authority of Thailand has continuously encouraged Thais to understand their Thai identities and the value of their historical sites, culture and tradition.

The tourism resources have recently been moving toward sustainable tourism [2]. The sustainable tourism industry in Thailand has achieved this. At the present, there are many aspects to manage effectively including various signs to the important places. There are some problems to group of tourists which are not clear such as signs to tell ways, signs for educational information of tourism sources. The location signs are only in the Thai language which can make it difficult for foreign tourists to understand. The information shows that the Thai identity is extremely necessary and important as a tourism resource. The way that the identity of the tourism resources is communicated is very important to help tourists understand and learn these ideals [6]. These groups are important to Thai tourism resources at Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram Province. In this research, The Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram Province is identified by: the History of Amphawa District, Samut Songkham, the History of King Rama II Memorial Park, the Prominent Amphawa Floating Market, and learning sources of the ecosystem of fireflies and cork trees. These topics are useful for both the Thai people and foreign tourists. The important problems took place at Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram province. The communication to foreigners in English is the least important [7]. These situations may reduce the number of foreign visitors.

For this research, the researcher chose the Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram province to be the research area. This area is very interesting to foreign tourists and helps them understand the Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram province. ICOMOS (The International Council on Monuments and Sites) tries to communicate new events in the communities and the past civilization at the same time [4]. This function was too plain for the both the Thai people and the foreigner's younger generations to learn. If the researcher had not explored the topic for this paper, it is possible the Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram province would not understand

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this important tourism resource. The researcher is an English teacher who is interested in finding the identities of Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram province and the Design of English Materials to Communicate the Identity of Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram province, for sustainable tourism.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

1. To study the data and analyze the identities of the Identity of Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram Province, for Sustainable Tourism.
2. To communication the Identity of Amphur Amphawa develop the sustainable materials as a communication some sustainable tourism.

A. Mythology

This research is qualitative research. The objectives of this research are The Design of English Materials to Communicate the Identity of the Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram Province, for Sustainable Tourism.

B. Population and Samples

There are three groups of samples that are outlined in the following items:

1. The key informant group in the Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram province is five persons: the chief persons and officers in the Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram province.
2. The foreigner group is made up of ten people per day who visited Thailand. The researcher interviewed the thirty people for the foreigner group by the following criterions:

- 2.1 The foreigner group who had come in the Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram province, Thailand more than one time.
- 2.2 The foreigner group who specially visited the Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram province, Thailand, and did not go to any other places.
- 2.3 In this case for the foreigner group, if a group included two persons traveling together only one person was chosen for the interview.

There are also the following conditions:

1. The age of the tourists interviewed is more than twenty years old.
2. There are six tourists from Europe, seven tourists from America, four tourists from Australia, seven tourists from Canada and six tourists from Asia.

TABLE I
GROUP OF KEY INFORMANTS IN THE AMPHUR AMPHAWA SAMUT SONGKRAM PROVINCE

General data of group of key informant	Gender		Age				Level of Education	
	F	M	25	31	36	45	B	M
			-	-	-	-		
			30	35	40	50		
Key informant group in Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram province	3	2	1	2	1	1	1	4
Total	3	2	1	2	1	1	1	4

TABLE II
GROUP OF FOREIGNER TOURISTS WHO CAME TO THE AMPHUR AMPHAWA SAMUT SONGKRAM PROVINCE

Samples Group	Gender		Age				Times Level of Visiting Education				
	F	M	22-30	31-40	41-50	51-60	61-70	1	2	B	M
Europe	4	2	1	2	3	2	0	3	4	4	2
America	2	5	1	1	2	0	1	2	3	3	2
Australia	4	0	2	2	0	0	0	6	2	4	2
Canada	5	1	1	3	2	0	0	2	2	4	2
Asia	4	3	2	1	4	0	0	4	1	5	2
Total	19	11	7	9	11	2	1	18	12	20	10

TABLE III
GROUP OF TOURIST GUIDES

Samples group	Gender		Age			Working Experience		Level of Education		Number
	M	F	25-35	36-45	46-55	2-5	6-10	11-15		
Group of Tourist guides	1	4	3	1	1	1	1	1	5	5
Total	1	4	3	1	1	1	1	1	5	5

III. DELIMITATION OF RESEARCH PROPOSAL

A. Delimitation of Research Proposal

During this research, the researcher conducted the study at the Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram province, Thailand, to study the data to analyze the identity and communication at the Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram province, for sustainable tourism. This study was conducted from October

2010 to September 2012 by triangulation methodology such as observations, asking questions, taking notes on the data and checking documents.

B. Conceptual Framework

Literature Review was conducted on the theory of sustainable tourism, the theory of communication, the theory of Semiology and other research for the conceptual frameworks for the following items:

The identities of the Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram province

1. The History of the Amphawa District, Samut Songkham
2. The History of King Rama II Memorial Park
3. The Prominent Amphawa Floating Market
4. Learning Source of Ecosystem: Fireflies and Cork Trees
5. How to keep Amphawa Amphur for sustainable tourism

C. Research Instruments

The researcher used the qualitative method for this research. The research instruments consisted of in-depth interviews, direct observation and content analysis of written materials with the details below:

The interview was used in the unstructured-interview with both the Thai language and English language. The questions were divided by sample groups into the following items: Interview for key informant group in the Amphawa, District Samut Songkram province had two parts, each is listed below:

Part I General information of interviewers consisted of name, surname, gender, age, education, status, and position at Amphawa District, Samut Songkram province.

Part II The Interview Questions are listed below:

1. The History of Amphawa District, Samut Songkram
2. The History of King Rama II Memorial Park
3. The Prominent Amphawa Floating Market
4. Learning Source of Ecosystem: Fireflies and Cork Trees
5. How to keep Amphawa District for sustainable tourism

Interview for tourist guides had two parts, each is listed below:

Part I General information of interviewers consisted of name, surname, gender, age, education, status, position at the Amphawa, District Samut Songkram province.

Part II The Interview Questions are listed below:

1. How do you know the Amphawa District, Samut Songkram province?
2. What is the identity of the Amphawa District in Samut Songkram province according to your own idea? Please give examples.
3. What do you want to communicate to others about the Amphawa District in Samut Songkram province?
4. In what matters do foreign tourists recognize the Amphawa District in Samut Songkram province?
5. How can you help preserving the Amphawa District in Samut Songkram province for sustainable tourism?
6. What are your suggestions to promote tourism at this tourist attraction?
7. What are the problems that affect foreign tourists at the Amphawa District in Samut Songkram province?
8. How do you keep Amphawa District in Samut Songkram province for sustainable tourism?
9. What are the big images of the Amphawa District in Samut Songkram province according to you?

D. Observations

Observations were collected to provide a content analysis of written materials at the Amphawa District in Samut Songkram province. They consisted of the contents analysis to communicate about the Amphawa District in Samut Songkram province, Amphawa floating market in the evening and nearby environmental areas.

E. Records the Conversation in a Group

Workshop

The data was collected from field trips and separated by each categorical variables topic of research.

Taking notes

The researcher took notes at each interview and used equipment such as a recorder, a camera, etc.

Data Collection

1. Survey Study

The researcher collected the data by reviewing of literature and documents related to surveyed areas and collected the data from literature that were related to surveyed areas of the Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram province.

2. Key Informants

The researcher had an appointment with the five key informants for in-depth interview at the Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram province.

3. Group of Tourists

The researcher interviewed the tourists who visited the Amphur Amphawa, Samut Songkram province by interviewing thirty tourists from Europe, America and Asia.

4. Tourist Guides

The researcher asked the five tourist guides the following questions in their interviews.

IV. ANALYZING THE DATA AND WRITING THE RESEARCH REPORT

The researcher collected the data from the interviews, studied the data and the documents and analyzed the content analysis. The researcher used the data of interviews from key informants, foreigner tourists and tourist guides. The researcher took photographs and recorded the documents. After that, the researcher gathered the conclusion from the answers and discussions in a research report following the **conceptual framework** and the theories outlined in this paper. The researcher described the report and related information in the content analysis.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This report analyzed "The design of English materials to communicate the identity of the Amphawa, District Samut Songkram province for sustainable tourism by the following five items:

1. The History of the Amphawa District, Samut Songkram
2. The History of King Rama II Memorial Park
3. The Prominent Amphawa Floating Market
4. Learning Source of Ecosystem: Fireflies and Cork Trees
5. How to keep Amphawa Amphur for sustainable tourism

The sustainable tourism has occurred because of the affections of the national resources [1]. It was a center of learning about natural resources, a pleasure to view the

mangrove forest scenery, plants and animals including mangroves, cork trees and fireflies. They were found in Cembalos' research, 2010. And Bushel's 'research in Interpretation in National Parks: Some Critical Questions. The communication for the natural resources found that the communication should be geared toward ecotourism and stress the knowledge and the suggestions in the natural resources crossing the cultural divide: Western visitors and interpretation at Ayutthaya World Heritage Site, Thailand. The researcher found that the communication should show the highlight, preparing the manual for services and giving the information to the information center [10]. Moreover, it should create leaflets and a CD of the Amphawa District, Samut Songkram province. The communication should show meaning and important things which were found in [8]. Reference [3] mentioned the communication showed the information and true facts. Offering every type of communication means giving the information and presenting it for studying the English for tourism subject. It made the tourists feel better and better understand the content. It increased the tourists' morale to protect the natural environments for local persons, tourist guides and government officers who were responsible the natural resources [5]. The communication in the English language is very important for the Amphawa District, Samut Songkram province, for sustainable tourism. Studying the identities of the natural resources by using the English language made it easier to communicate to the foreign tourists to understand the identity of the other natural resources in Thailand.

Suggestion for the Next Research

This research can be applied to the next research on other natural resources or historical sites, tradition and culture where searches for the identity of local culture are needed any sites that is interested in sustainable tourism in the future would be a good location to study.

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